

Research Article

Measuring the Ethics Understanding & their Behaviour among University Students: A Study at UiTM Kelantan Branch

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Abstract: This article seeks to assess the ethical awareness and conduct of undergraduate students at the UiTM Kelantan Branch. It goes into greater detail about the effects of gender and academic fields on these four moral processes. Malaysian undergraduates from the UiTM Kelantan Branch totalled 200 for the study. Based on the information received from the survey, 14 ethical statements were created. Data analysis techniques included descriptive analysis (using measures like mean), and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). However, this survey managed to collect data from 214 respondents. In order to obtain this information and data, quantitative data collection activities were conducted through questionnaires among the students involved. The majority of the average responses from this survey indicate that undergraduate students at the University of Kelantan have an average level of ethics. However, Cronbach's Alpha accomplishment findings demonstrate that the survey's stated questions are reliable given a sample size of 30 respondents Cronbach's Alpha getting ≥ 0.7 .

Keywords: Students; Ethics; Academic faculty, gender, behaviours

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ethical awareness should be a big concern by teaching ethical values, good morals, and integrity from childhood and continuing the good morals taught to higher students in education. This ongoing teaching in ethics may result in students who maintain the moral principles they have learned in class and future professionals equipped to handle moral conflicts when entering the workforce. According to (O'Leary, 2009), ethics can be referred to as even while a person is sensitive to or aware of ethical situations, this does not necessarily imply how their decision will turn out. Early exposure to moral issues is needed, especially for university students, who should receive instruction to gain specialisation in dealing with moral problems when facing the future. According to (Moore & Gino, 2013), when people are aware of the essential moral principles and the possible effects of their choices, they are more likely to act ethically. Controlling emotion also can be included in good morals. It is because when we are mad and in uncontrolled emotion, we are likely to do nonsense things. According

to (Aquino et al. 2011, Schnall et al. 2010), positive moral emotion can be included in ethical attitudes as well. The objective of this study is twofold: first, this study determines the ethics among undergraduate students in the UiTM Kelantan Branch, based on processes, judgment, awareness, morals, behaviour, and intention. The second objective is that this paper also wants to identify differences between faculty, gender, and their level of ethics. According to (Haynes, 1998,) ethics should be a big concern since it is not only an ethical problem but also responsible for the next generation. It is crucial to learn ethics, especially for students in higher education since ethics can help with better decision-making.

Moreover, as the next generation of leaders, higher education students look forward to achieving Malaysia's aim to grow an ethical community by the year 2023. According to YAB, Minister Dato' Seri Anwar Ibrahim has encouraged us to develop "Malaysia Madani", which will make Malaysia respected and known as a flourishing nation. In order to achieve "Malaysia Madani", good values, trust, fairness, and governance is essential. Therefore, in 2023, UiTM will be one of the universities that will grab the opportunities to develop Malaysia Madani by focusing on globally marketable activities linked to the strategic plan UiTM 2025 towards becoming the best university in the world. According to (Ndoye, 2002), good education management also can contribute to national development and the quality of education is important which is related with ethical behaviour. Then, Good morals also can improve leadership which is a needed characteristic to become a leader. According to (Hassan, 2015; Hassan et al., 2014; Lu & Guy, 2014), good values and morals of a leader could impact the effectiveness of the leadership which lead to a successful growth of an organization especially in education. If a leader shows a good ethical behaviour such as fairness, honesty and trustworthy for the fellow student, the student will follow the ethical morals either and this is because they tend to follow what they have watched and seen since a leader is always describe as a role model as according to (Brown and Treviño, 2006; Lee et al., 2010) mentioned that followers look out for the behaviours of their ethical leaders, consider them as attractive and reliable role models, and eventually learn to copy those behaviours. Meanwhile, according to Eisenberger et al. (2001), specific action coming from a leader could impact work behaviour for the followers. Furthermore, according to (Gardelli, 2014: 19), schools have a big potential in helping students to develop morality and have a good life. When students have good morals, they will become more successful. That is why ethical education since childhood is a must so the children will have good morals and a sense of humour reflecting their situation. Not only that but continuing ethical education to higher students in universities also is needed to help the student have better decision-making based on good values since they will be the next generation of leaders in this country.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The selected research topic is "Measuring the ethics understanding & their behaviour among university students: a study in UiTM Kelantan branch". The survey that has been created was an intention for UiTM Kelantan's students regarding their understanding and behaviour regarding ethics. Therefore, the quantitative survey has been made in UiTM Kelantan as we are from there to collect the data from the students and lecturers.

The questionnaires have been divided into a few categories of graduations in the institution of Kelantan. Those categories include ages, courses, level of education, and religion. Based on the academics or courses, the data collected among the students are influenced by the results of ethics surveys. The distinctions across academic disciplines, due to the nature of work, motivate the present study to examine whether academic discipline impacts students' ethical perceptions. Ethical issues in research are of the utmost importance in 2019, according to the Centre for Innovation in Research and Teaching (CIRT). The main goal of the research is to gather information and the truth; ethical norms act

as protections against the fabrication or falsification of data. In collaborative work, ethical conduct is significant since it helps to create a culture of trust, responsibility, and respect among researchers. This becomes extremely important when dealing with issues like data sharing, co-authorship, copyright regulations, confidentiality, and other associated concerns.

It is essential to uphold ethical standards if a person wants the public to accept and believe in their study. The general public anticipates that scientists will adhere to rules governing human rights, animal welfare, legal compliance, conflicts of interest, safety, health standards, and other ethical issues. The integrity of the research project is substantially impacted by how these ethical difficulties are handled, which also impacts its chance of receiving funding.

According to research, the gender differences are also affecting the results of surveys. For example, according to the article that we referred to "Ethics of Undergraduate Students: A Study in Malaysian Public Universities" (Rodzalan & Saat, 2016), the studies have looked at student ethics, paying particular attention to gender disparities. According to most of this research, female students generally display higher ethical behaviour than their male counterparts. For instance, a recent study [18] indicated that female students demonstrated higher moral and religious beliefs. Apart from that, according to the same article also, another study examined the ethical practices of 725 business students across five universities. Female students displayed more outstanding ethical behaviour than male students, according to the results of a survey asking participants to score a list of 17 ethical behaviours. In particular, they rejected preferential treatment by refusing presents or favours and were less likely to take organisational equipment for personal use. Therefore, the results support a study by [20], which discovered that female students were less likely to cheat than male students. This discrepancy might be explained by the potential adverse effects of cheating, like suspending their education. Most of the research examined in this context indicates that female students are more likely to be ethical than male students, displaying higher levels of honesty, religiosity, and a decreased desire to cheat.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Demographics*

A survey has been conducted among students at UiTM Kelantan with students needing to answer some questions to achieve the survey result. The question comes with two parts, part A and Part B. Part A is focused on demographic questions, including gender, age, religion, and faculty. The students were provided with some choices as their answer. For age, students can choose from 18 to 20, 21 to 25, 26 to 30 and more than 31. The highest average age level is between the ages of 21 and 25, with an average of 73.8 per cent.

In contrast, the second highest age level falls between the ages of 18 and 20, where the average is only 22.8 per cent, and age level of 25 to 30 is the lowest rating with only 2.8 percent. Furthermore, for gender, there is a female and male choice in the survey. The female gender outperformed the male gender in this survey, collecting an average of 63.1 percent of the data to the male gender's 36.9 percent. This shows female students are more concerned about ethics compared to male students. Meanwhile, for the religion, there were Islam, Buddha, Tamil, and others for students to choose from most of the respondents are Muslim; there is also Campus Kota Bharu and Machang choice since UiTM Kelantan Branch is divided into two small branches. Most of the data collected is from students in the Machang branch, where the average percentage is 72 percent, and only 16.8 percent collected data from Campus in Kota Bharu. Moreover, level of study is also a concern in this demographic section which involves Pre-Commerce, Diploma, Degree and Master and Degree is the highest rating with 69.6 percent. Then, faculty, there were six faculty participating in this survey which are Faculty of Accountancy with 11.7

per cent collected data and Faculty of Business & Management with 8.9 percent. Same as the Faculty of Administrative Science & Policy Studies. Meanwhile, for the Faculty of Computer Science & Mathematics collected data is 26.6 percent and for the College of Creative Art is 9.3 percent and the highest rating is from the Faculty of Information Management with 34.6 collected data. All students in the UiTM Kelantan Branch have an impact on the demographic data of each student enrolled in this survey, including gender, age, religion, and faculty.

3.2 knowledge and understanding about ethics

Good questions are essential to put into a questionnaire to achieve the goals of a survey. This survey is involved with two parts which are Part A and Part B. For this Part B, students were provided with a few questions relating to knowledge and understanding about ethics. There were 14 questions provided. Which first question is about "I behave unethically when asked to do so by my lecturers even though it contradicted my ethical principle", which collected 56.10 percent, and "When my lecturers asked me to do something unethical, I was committed to showing my obedience" is 47.7 percent, and for "I behave unethically (i.e., plagiarised, stealing) because of pressures (ie. time and cost constraint)" is 43.0 percent and for the next question "I prefer not to report friends' unethical behaviour to lecturers" is 38.3 percent is the highest rating meanwhile for "I commit unethical action when it is beyond my control (ie. I plagiarise because the academic system emphasises excellent results)" is 45.3 percent as a moderate choice. Moreover, "Using a copy machine, paper and other supplies for personal use is not unethical behaviour" is 41.1 percent and "I hold to my principle that honesty is important than getting good grade" is 37.9 as the highest rating and "I take full responsibility if I do any unethical action (ie. I confess if lecturers found me plagiarising some works) is 42.1 and for this question "I behave ethically in adherence to regulation and code of ethics outlined by university" is 39.3 percent as the highest rating. Then, for this question "I will take all opinions/considerations from others if I need to make a decision on ethical dilemma", is 40.7 percent, and "During my study in university, I referred to others to resolve ethical dilemmas" is 40.2 percent and for "I personally dealt with ethical dilemmas during studying in university" is 41.6 percent as moderate and for "I have been confronted with ethical dilemmas during studying in university" is 43.0 percent and for "The faculty (ie lecturers, administrator) will reward me when I do something ethical" is 32.2 Based on these 14 questionnaire, the first question "I behave unethically when asked to do so by my lecturers even though it contradicted my ethical principle" is the highest rating with moderate as an answer compared to other question. This shows students are confused about whether to stand on their principle or follow the lecturer's instruction due to respect and to maintain the relationship with the lecturers.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the result that has been conducted among students at UiTM Kelantan Branch, the result shows an unexpected answer as we expected to be. The survey was provided with 14 questions with strongly agree and strongly disagree as an answer.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I behave unethically when asked to do so by my lecturers even though it contradicted my ethical principle	212	1	5	2.81	.999
When my lecturers asked me to do something unethical, I was committed to show my obedience	212	1	5	2.80	1.098
I behave unethically (ie. plagiarized, stealing) because of pressures (ie. time and cost constraint)	212	1	5	2.96	1.045
I prefer not to report friends' unethical behaviour to lecturers	212	1	5	3.09	1.084
I commit unethical action when it is beyond my control (ie. I plagiarize because the academic system emphasis on excellent results)	212	1	5	3.00	1.082
Using a copy machine, paper and other supplies for personal use is not unethical behaviour.	212	1	5	3.17	.985
I hold to my principle that honesty is important than getting good grade.	212	1	5	3.63	.927
I take full responsibility if I do any unethical action (ie. I confess if lecturers found me plagiarize some works)	212	1	5	3.65	.898
I behave ethically in adherence to regulation and code of ethics outlined by university.	212	1	5	3.66	.875
I will take all opinions/considerations from others if I need to make a decision on ethical dilemma.	212	1	5	3.68	.877
During my study in university, I referred to others to resolve ethical dilemmas.	212	1	5	3.57	.871
I personally dealt with ethical dilemmas during studying in university	212	1	5	3.59	.868
I have been confronted with ethical dilemmas during studying in university	212	1	5	3.61	.821
The faculty (ie lecturers, administrator) will reward me when I do something ethical	212	1	5	3.22	1.094
Valid N (listwise)	212				

Table 2. Analysis of Variance ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
I behave unethically when asked to do so by my lecturers even though it contradicted my ethical principle	Between Groups	.073	1	.073	.073	.787
	Within Groups	210.380	210	1.002		
	Total	210.453	211			
When my lecturers asked me to do something unethical, I was committed to show my obedience	Between Groups	.509	1	.509	.421	.517
	Within Groups	253.769	210	1.208		
	Total	254.278	211			
I behave unethically (ie. plagiarized, stealing) because of pressures (ie. time and cost constraint)	Between Groups	.815	1	.815	.744	.389
	Within Groups	229.803	210	1.094		
	Total	230.618	211			
I prefer not to report friends' unethical behaviour to lecturers	Between Groups	.417	1	.417	.354	.553
	Within Groups	247.696	210	1.180		
	Total	248.113	211			
I commit unethical action when it is beyond my control (ie. I plagiarize because the academic system emphasis on excellent results)	Between Groups	2.279	1	2.279	1.956	.163
	Within Groups	244.716	210	1.165		
	Total	246.995	211			
Using a copy machine, paper and other supplies for personal use is not unethical behaviour.	Between Groups	.030	1	.030	.030	.862
	Within Groups	204.513	210	.974		
	Total	204.542	211			

Table 2 presents the ANOVA results which show that there are differences in the level of ethics based on academic discipline. The differences were highly significant in all negative and positive statements as $p < 0.01$. The faculty of administrative science and policy studies received the lowest score when compared to the faculty of information management, which can be used to further analyse the disparities in these claims. At this point, The mean difference between the six items that were chosen from the 14 that were included in this questionnaire can be seen using the ANOVA method. We may effectively compare data calculations and data observation methods using this method as well.

Table 3. (Question 1) I behave unethically when asked to do so by my lecturers even though it contradicted my ethical principle.

		behave			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	36	16.8	16.8	16.8
	2	16	7.5	7.5	24.3
	3	120	56.1	56.1	80.4
	4	36	16.8	16.8	97.2
	5	6	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

For the first question, the result shows most of the respondents choose moderate as the answer, 56.1 percent. This is because the student is confused whether to do or not since it was an instruction from the lecturer. The students who choose not to do it even if it was an instruction for the lecturer has a strong mindset and principle. Meanwhile, a student who did the unethical thing that was instructed by the lecturer may do it out of respect for the lecturer. Moreover, the data regarding the answer strongly disagree and agree recorded the same percentage which is 16.8 percent, and the lowest percentage is strongly agreed which is only 2.8 percent only. For instance, it shows that only a few respondents (2.8 percent) behave unethically when doing their instructions even though it contradicts their ethical principle while most respondents were moderate (56.1 percent). The highest average mean is 3.00 and it is those aged 26 to 30 years old, while the lowest average mean is 1.00 and it is among those aged 31 years and above.

Table 4. (Question 2) When my lecturers asked me to do something unethical, I was committed to showing my obedience.

		lecturers			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	45	21.0	21.0	21.0
	2	14	6.5	6.5	27.6
	3	102	47.7	47.7	75.2
	4	46	21.5	21.5	96.7
	5	7	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

Next, the findings indicate that 47.7 percent of respondents do not actually support the stated question, with none of them expressing either excessive agreement with the assertions made or experimenting with them. Therefore, the data clearly shows that the respondents have a difficult decision whether they agree or disagree with the question they are facing. It is possible that students do not understand the question a hundred percent even though the question is asked as they have to do something unethical that is asked by their lecturers. Only 21.5 percent strongly agree, representing 45 respondents and almost half from the highest respondents whereas 47.7 percent (102 respondents). It concludes that some of the respondents still understand the question. The highest average mean is 3.00 and it is those aged 26 to 30 years old, while the lowest average mean is 1.00 and it is among those aged 31 years and above.

Table 5. (Question 3) I behave unethically (i.e., plagiarised, stealing) because of pressures (ie. time and cost constraint).

		unethically			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	32	15.0	15.0	15.0
	2	21	9.8	9.8	24.8
	3	92	43.0	43.0	67.8
	4	63	29.4	29.4	97.2
	5	6	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

Then, for this question, the result shows "I behave unethically such as plagiarising and stealing because of pressure" is moderate with 43.0 percent who cannot ascertain whether they are involved in plagiarism and stealing. This behaviour demonstrates negative qualities. However, the data was able to get information from 32 students, and the percentage of those who did not engage in immoral behaviour like plagiarism and stealing because of pressure was 15.0 percent. The second highest data is agreed that 29.4 percent define 63 respondents whereas 2: 3 with the answer for moderate (43.0 percent = 63 respondents). The results seem almost the students that are admit that they behave unethically because of pressures (ie. time and cost constraint). As students want a short way to complete their tasks so that they can complete their tasks according to submission date that have been given. The highest average mean is 3.50 and it is those aged 26 to 30 years old, while the lowest average mean is 1.00 and it is among those aged 31 years and above.

Table 6. (Question 4) I prefer not to report friends' unethical behaviour to lecturers.

		friends			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	28	13.1	13.1	13.1
	2	21	9.8	9.8	22.9
	3	82	38.3	38.3	61.2
	4	70	32.7	32.7	93.9
	5	13	6.1	6.1	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

Other than that, according to question number 4, the results showed that there are two answers that have a competitive percentage. It is between 3 and 4 which are natural and agree (38.3 percent, 32.7 percent). The Agreed answer is the second highest percentage in the data above. Basically, most of the students agree (32.7 percent second highest data) to not report their friend's unethical behaviour to the lecturers. It seems that students prefer to not expose their friend's behaviour to the lecturers. At the same time, only 6.1 percent (the lowest data recorded) prefer to back up their friends even though they know that their friends have the wrong attitude. In comparison, the respondents that answered naturally might not be sure which is the right way to take action whenever their friends do unethical behaviour during the time. The highest average mean is 3.50 and it is those aged 26 to 30 years old, while the lowest average mean is 1.00 and it is among those aged 31 years and above.

Table 7. (Question 5) I commit unethical action when it is beyond my control (ie. I plagiarise because the academic system emphasises excellent results).

		plagiarize			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	32	15.0	15.0	15.0
	2	17	7.9	7.9	22.9
	3	97	45.3	45.3	68.2
	4	55	25.7	25.7	93.9
	5	13	6.1	6.1	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

Next, according to the data for the fifth question, the question asked whether the students commit unethical behaviour when it is beyond their control (I plagiarise because the academic system emphasises excellent results). The highest percentage is the answer moderate, 45.3 percent representing 97 respondents. While the second highest percentage is 25.7 percent, define 55 frequencies for an agreed answer. It shows almost all the respondents admit their unethical behaviour during the study process, for example, plagiarising the article whenever completing their tasks. Apart from that, there are a few frequencies that answered strongly disagree with 15.0 percent (32 frequency). It concludes that these days, there are still some students who are being honest towards their responsibility in completing their assignments among UiTM students. The highest average mean is 5.00 and it is those who are over 31 years old and above, while the lowest mean average is 2.81 and it is among those aged 18 to 20 years old.

Table 8. (Question 6) Using a copy machine, paper and other supplies for personal use is not unethical behaviour.

		machine			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	16	7.5	7.5	7.5
	2	28	13.1	13.1	20.6
	3	88	41.1	41.1	61.7
	4	68	31.8	31.8	93.5
	5	14	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

Furthermore, for the "using a copy machine, paper and other supplies for personal use is not unethical behaviour" question, the result shows that the respondent chose moderate as their answer 41.1 percent, ten percent higher than the answer for agree, which is 31.8 percent. It may be that they are used to using the tools that make them feel that behaviour is not unethical. This is due to the possibility that it will somewhat aid them in finishing the jobs they excel at. In fact, it can assist students in adding more information to their articles and drawing similarities with their own work. However, there are also few answers that strongly disagree, for 7.5 percent representing 16 frequencies. It seems these

respondents do not think that using a copy machine, paper and other supplies for personal use is not unethical behaviour. The highest average mean is 3.50 which is among those aged 26 to 30 years, while the lowest average mean is 1.00 among those aged 31 and over.

Table 9. (Question 7) For the statement part of the question, "I stick to my principle that honesty is important to get a good grade"

		principle			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	5	2.3	2.3	2.3
	2	13	6.1	6.1	8.4
	3	81	37.9	37.9	46.3
	4	74	34.6	34.6	80.8
	5	41	19.2	19.2	100.0
Total		214	100.0	100.0	

This survey was able to collect a frequency of 81 respondents who selected response number 3, and the percentage derived from this frequency is 37.9 percent. The data gathered shows that almost half of the population believes that being honest throughout the exam can help students succeed and earn a decent score as opposed to engaging in exam cheating. However, five students were polled on their opinions, and they found that none of them agreed that answering honestly on the test would improve their marks. Additionally, the percentage result based on the five times more disagreeable votes is 2.3 percent. This has demonstrated that there are still college students in Kelantan who have been found guilty of duplicating answers during exams. The highest mean is 5.00 and it is those who are over 31 years old, but the lowest average mean is 3.48 and they are in the age range of 18 to 20 years.

Table 10. (Question 8) Meanwhile, for this question, "I take full responsibility if I do any unethical action (I confess if lecturers found me plagiarising some works).

		responsibility			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3	1.4	1.4	1.4
	2	11	5.1	5.1	6.5
	3	90	42.1	42.1	48.6
	4	66	30.8	30.8	79.4
	5	44	20.6	20.6	100.0
Total		214	100.0	100.0	

For this part it is rated as moderate as well with 42.1 percent. According to the data gathered through this study, there are 1.4 percent of students who decide not to inform and accept their fault if they are found committing a mistake, with a frequency of three times. It's possible that they're worried about the penalty they'll get later. It is a little bit disappointing since the students are not choosing to strongly agree with their answer. The highest mean number is 3.75 and it is those who are in the age group of 21 to 25 years old. But the lowest is 1.00 among those aged 31 and above.

Table 11. (Question 9). Next, for the survey question, "I behave ethically in adherence to regulation and code of ethics outlined by the university having two answers that are almost the same.

adherence					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	5	2.3	2.3	2.3
	2	7	3.3	3.3	5.6
	3	84	39.3	39.3	44.9
	4	80	37.4	37.4	82.2
	5	38	17.8	17.8	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

There are moderate and second strongly agree (4). The percentage for moderates is 39.3 percent with 84 respondents, while the percentage for second strongly agrees at 37.4 percent with 80 respondents. When the data gathered revealed that among the students who responded to this survey question, the frequency of votes was five times against this statement, and the percentage acquired was as high as 2.3 percent, it is pretty upsetting. This has demonstrated the university's failure to uphold moral and civic behaviour among its students at all times. The highest mean number recorded for this section is 4.00 and it covers among those aged 26 to 30 years, and the lowest mean number is 1.00 recorded among students who are over 31 years old.

Table 12. (Question 10) "I will take all opinions/considerations from others if I need to make a decision on an ethical dilemma".

opinions					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	4	1.9	1.9	1.9
	2	7	3.3	3.3	5.1
	3	87	40.7	40.7	45.8
	4	74	34.6	34.6	80.4
	5	42	19.6	19.6	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

The question's statement for this problem's level discusses how students should resolve ethical dilemmas by consulting outside sources, such as people and examples. Despite this, students consistently choose option three and continue to have doubts about the validity of the source they used; 40.7 percent of students chose this option, choosing to agree or disagree. If they face this moral conundrum, it's likely that they will decide to find a solution on their own rather than consulting any sources or other individuals. Next, the highest mean recorded is 3.72 and it is in the range of those aged 21 to 25 years, while the lowest is 1.00, and this number is recorded from the age group of 31 years and above.

Table 13. (Question 11) “During my study in university, referred to others to resolve ethical dilemmas”.

		during			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	6	2.8	2.8	2.8
	2	10	4.7	4.7	7.5
	3	86	40.2	40.2	47.7
	4	83	38.8	38.8	86.4
	5	29	13.6	13.6	100.0
Total		214	100.0	100.0	

In the survey, the average student reported that only 40.2 percent of the data collected indicated that they either strongly disagreed or did not strongly disagree with the statements in this question. Additionally, the fact that most students have doubts about their ability to solve these ethical conundrums while in college is demonstrated by the ethical dilemma-solving section of the study. "When I attended university, I was faced with a moral conundrum." The majority of students, according to 40.2 percent of respondents, are not sure if they have faced ethical dilemmas while in college. In fact, this figure shows that even if the average student is at a good level, they are concerned about ethical difficulties when they attend university. However, given that 2.8 percent of survey participants said they actually met this ethical conundrum while at university, it's likely that half of them were exposed to similar moral dilemmas. For the mean part, the most recorded the highest mean amount of 3.67 among the age group 26 to 30 years old. While the lowest mean is 1.00 among those aged 31 and above.

Table 14. (Question 12) “I personally dealt with ethical dilemmas during studying in university”.

		dealt			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3	1.4	1.4	1.4
	2	13	6.1	6.1	7.5
	3	89	41.6	41.6	49.1
	4	73	34.1	34.1	83.2
	5	36	16.8	16.8	100.0
Total		214	100.0	100.0	

The number of frequencies acquired is 89 times, and the calculated percentage rate is 41.6, indicating that students are still having second thoughts about their choice. However, the information gathered also managed to identify pupils whose frequency is three and included 1.4 percent who were unable to regulate the pomegranate's manners while enrolled in university courses. This has actually exposed the unethical side of the students who must grapple with this moral conundrum. As a matter of fact, this may have an impact on their accomplishments, their health, and other aspects of their lives. The university must also take action on this matter to inform professors about the significance and drawbacks of issues like these. For the mean part, the most the average age that has the highest mean level of 3.66 is 21 to 25 years. While the lowest mean is among those over 30 years old and recorded a mean total of 1.00.

Table 15. (Question 13) “I have been confronted with ethical dilemmas during studying in university”.

		confronted			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	2	.9	.9	.9
	2	10	4.7	4.7	5.6
	3	92	43.0	43.0	48.6
	4	77	36.0	36.0	84.6
	5	33	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

This question is intended to find out if other students at the University of Kelantan are experiencing ethical problems, as I did while I was a student there. The proportion calculated using the highest frequency of 92 students who selected answer number 3 is 43 percent. Most of the students who selected option number 3 were unsure of whether they had truly encountered this ethical conundrum or not. Additionally, there was the lowest frequency recorded, which was that a small number of students disagreed with the total frequency recorded of 2. Based on the frequency of these two individuals, the percentage recorded is 9 percent, clearly demonstrating that these students have never encountered this ethical dilemma. However, the response to this question in the survey revealed a sad fact when there were 33 frequencies and the percentage recorded was 15.4 per cent of respondents who selected they had encountered this issue while in college. It is hoped that the institution will recognise and address people who encounter this issue. The mean for this question who have the highest number are those in the age group over 30 years old who recorded a mean number of 5.00. However, the lowest mean is among the age group of 26 to 30 years old who recorded a mean total of only 3.62.

Table 16. (Question 14) For the last question “The faculty (i.e., lecturers, administrator) will reward me when I do something ethical.”.

		administrator			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	10	4.7	4.7	4.7
	2	50	23.4	23.4	28.0
	3	69	32.2	32.2	60.3
	4	54	25.2	25.2	85.5
	5	31	14.5	14.5	100.0
	Total	214	100.0	100.0	

The data reveals that most students' responses to this final question are not confident or certain; this is because most of their university faculties do not and do not usually reward students; the highest average found was only 32.2 percent nonetheless, the frequency for this percentage is 69. However, ten students claimed that neither the university nor their professors had ever given them anything to cheer them up when they had success while they were students. This has demonstrated that the students who responded to the survey are distraught and are still unsure of whether the university recognizes their accomplishments or not. This is a very unfortunate development since it may have an impact on how well future students perform. At this point, the highest of mean is 4.00 among the age from 26 until 30, while the lowest mean for this question is among the undergraduate students age more than 30. The mean for this age is only 1.00.

5. CONCLUSION

Ethic is a crucial component that must be taken care of and ingrained in each person to shape them towards a better; for instance, a humane society can exist in a state of peace and harmony without encountering any issues or being subjected to inappropriate crimes, the author wants to emphasise the importance of ethics and morality in the individual to form a good and good individual. Because this journal exists, readers can consult it and learn how crucial ethics are in a solitary life because morality affects the attitudes and situations of those around them. Based on the result that has been conducted among the student UiTM Kelantan branch, we can assume that the students are not too open and less concerned with ethical issues. According to (Kohlberg (1969, 1981), we still can create a person to an ethical behaviour through ethical training which refers to education. Moreover, universities must add an ethics subject for each cost and faculty to expose the student to good behaviour, values, morals and attitude. According to (Ponemon, 1993; Bay and Greenberg, 2001; Thomas, 2004), even though students score high positive ratings on the ethical survey also could act unethically because they do not normalize the ethical education they have learnt. Ethical education is not the only thing that is essential and is not enough to lead the student to good behaviour but normalization also is a must to create an ethical student, environment, and education as Aristotle said “educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all”.

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